

ISic0268

I.Sicily inscription 0268

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus)
2. M(arcus) · Aemilius
3. Felicianus
4. scriba · pub(licus)
5. fidelissimus
6. v(ixit) · a(nnis) · XLIII
7. Nonia Zosima
8. marito · b(ene) · m(erenti)

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 and CIL

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Marcus Aemilius Felicianus, most trustworthy public scribe, died at 43 years. Nonia Zosima (erected this) for her well deserving husband.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284765
EDR 033605
EDCS 21900298
PHI 313699

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6979 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At xvii

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